

GLOBALIZATION VERSUS CHITRALI CULTURAL HERITAGE: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Nowadays globalization has a big role in the diversity of culture. The current study is based on both literary as well as field information which explore the impact of globalization on culture heritage. In order to study the relationship between globalization and culture the relevant literature has been reviewed, where the empirical data was collected based on simple size of 48 participants through random sampling and convenient sampling technique. The data has been collected through structure interview schedule and interview guide, while the data has been further analyzed statically in table and chart form.

INTRODUCTION

Culture is the shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices that are transmitted from generation to generation and that define a group's identity and guides its member behavior" (Khalid, 2021). Culture is the way of living that shows similarities and differences among people in a different region (Khan, 2022). Every region or society have its unique culture which show its qualities that make them distinguish from other people of the society. Moreover, "culture is the distinguishing mark of human social group. All human group possess it, though in different degrees and qualities (Ellwood, 1918)". Now, in the modern age of life with the advanced in the technology and communications the whole universe now became a global village, where people can easily communicate and connected with one another sharing their values and beliefs that pave way to culture hybridity (Aziz, 2024).

In the modern age, globalization has effected every individual, which is associated with homogenization, polarization, and hybridization of culture and chart (Martell, 2007). However, each individual is effected on a different scale, For example, globalization has affected the first world countries more than developing countries, because developed countries has the capacity to afford the cost of internet and other thing that are the product of modernity and they also allow flexibility in their culture (Black, 2000). However, the developing country has an indigenous culture so they don't allow any variation in their culture, for example china's restriction on internet is good example of isolating their inhabitant from the world view (Roudmetof, 1994). Nevertheless, it has been observed that globalization has changed the entire world heritage which includes change in the indigenous language, food, fashion, and values too

(Lowenthal,2013). Analysis the secondary information and the availability of resources, the current study is based upon the rational study on the impact of globalization on Chitral culture heritage, and to study how globalization playing a dominant role in the homogenization of the entire culture heritage. The specific objectives of the study are as given below (Fatima, 2023).

Objectives of the study:

Followings are the specifics objectives of the study:

- I.To assess the perceptions of Chitral residents regarding the impact of digitalization on their culture heritage.
- II.To identify the specific culture heritage, elements that is most affected by digitalization.
- III.To gather recommendations from the residents of Chitral for preserving culture heritage in the digital age.

Hypothesis of the study:

The main hypotheses are as:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between globalization and hybridity on the culture heritage of Chitral.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between the globalization and the generational divide in attitudes toward Chitral cultural heritage.

Material and Methods

The nature of the current is qualitative in nature and based on the statistical analyzed only associations have been analyzed, while the quantitative analysis includes correlation test for explanation and clarity. The study was conducted in district Chitral, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. However, the data was collected from private, government schools and universities in the locality. In this regard, six educational institutions have given equal opportunities, and are selected randomly. However convenient and random sampling has been selected for the study. In this study both structure and un structure questionnaires has been used to collect the data from selected respondents based on the convenient sampling and random sampling, where the close ended questionnaires are based on the agreement of lickard scale. Besides, the data is analyzed through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) and thematic analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between globalization and hybridity of chital culture.

Impact of globalization on Chitral culture heritage:

Globalization has a significant impact on the culture heritage of any culture, the study of literary review shows that globalization influences culture identity from both the lens of challenges and opportunity (Hei, 2024). The analysis of field study show in table

1.1 presents’ responses to the statement, “modern fashion trends have negatively influenced Chitral cultural identity” Among the 48 valid responses, the majority, 24 respondents (50%), **strongly disagreed**, indicating that they do not feel modern fashion has negatively

impacted Chitral cultural identity. Another 7 respondents (14.6%) **disagreed**, while 6 respondents (12.5%) remained **neutral**. On the other hand, 7 respondents (14.6%) **agreed**, and 4 respondents (8.3%) **strongly agreed** with the statement(Kalash,

2022). This suggests that a considerable portion of respondents does not believe modern fashion trends are harming the local culture, though a small minority does, as shown in chart 1.

The table 1.1also shows responses to the statement, "The establishment of modern restaurants in Chitral has diminished the importance of traditional Chitral food." Out of 48 valid responses, 19 respondents (39.6%) **disagreed**, and 6 respondents (12.5%) **strongly disagreed**, indicating that a majority do not feel that modern restaurants have significantly impacted traditional food. However, 13

respondents (27.1%) **agreed** and 5 respondents (10.4%) **strongly agreed**, showing that a considerable minority believes that modern restaurants are diminishing the importance of traditional Chitral food. Additionally, 5 respondents (10.4%) remained **neutral**. This data a divided views, though more respondents lean towards disagreements, as shown in chart 2.

When the respondent were asked about "The introduction of global educational content in Chitral is reducing the importance of local Chitral heritage in schools." Out of 48 valid responses, a significant portion—20

respondents (41.7%)—**strongly agreed**, and 4 respondents (8.3%) **agreed**, indicating that nearly half of the respondents believe global educational content is diminishing the importance of Chitral local

heritage. On the other hand, 19 respondents (39.6%) **disagreed**, and 5 respondents (10.4%) **strongly disagreed**, showing that a substantial group disagrees

with this view. This suggests a split in opinion, with a slight difference as shown in chart 3.

Table 1.1: Impact of Globalization on chitral culture heritage

Statements	Agreement				
	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly agree	Strongly disagree
Modern fashion change culture heritage.	7(14.3)	7(14.3)	6(12.2)	24(8.2)	4((49.0)
Establishment of modern restaurants cause losing of traditional food in chitral.	13(26.5)	19(38.8)	5(10.2)	5(10.2)	6(10.2)
Introduction of modern education cause changing culture heritage of Chitral.	4(8.2)	19(38.8)	5((98.0)	5(40.8)	12(10.2)

Hypothesis verification

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between globalization and diminishing the culture heritage of Chitral.

The table 1.1 shows that there may or may not be a significant relationship between globalization and the culture.

HO₂. There is no significant relationship between the globalization and the generational divide in attitudes toward Chitral cultural heritage.

Hypothesis verification

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between globalization and diminishing the culture heritage of Chitral.

The table 1.1 shows that there may or may not be a significant relationship between globalization and the culture.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between the globalization and the generational divide in attitudes toward Chitral cultural heritage.

Globalization and generation divide attitude:

The table 1.2 results show a mixed response regarding whether the younger generation in Chitral is losing interest cultural heritage due to global influences. Out of 49 respondents, 16.7% strongly agree with the statement, while a larger portion, 29.2%, disagrees. An additional 27.1% agree, showing some concern about the impact of globalization, while 12.5% remain neutral on the issue. Notably, 14.6% strongly disagree, suggesting a divide in perceptions. These findings highlight a significant portion of disagreement, but a notable percentage concern and uncertainty about the impact of global influence on chitral cultural heritage (Jan et al. 2019).

globalization and generation divide attitude:

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Table 1.2 : Impact of globalization on the changing attitude towards their culture heritage

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly agree	8	16.3	16.7	16.7

	Disagree	14	28.6	29.2	45.8
	Neutral	6	12.2	12.5	58.3
	Agree	13	26.5	27.1	85.4
	Strongly DA	7	14.3	14.6	100.0
	Total	48	98.0	100.0	
Total		49	100.0		

The mention hypothesis may or may not be rejected as the field information show a mix response on the claim.

As both of these hypotheses are rejected the current study is based on the two alternatives hypothesis as given below:

HI₁: There is a significant relationship between globalization and the culture change of chitral.

HI₂: There is a significant relationship between globalization and changing the attitude of chitral people towards their culture.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study conclude that globalization has a diverse impact on the culture of chitral .On one hand globalization is providing the opportunity to represent the culture heritage of chitral on national and international level as well as the economic opportunity to the inhabitants of chiral resident via promoting tourism in chitral region, while on the other other hand it is acting like threat for chitral culture by over shadowing its traditional way of life. As a result chitral culture will loses its identity by adopting other culture life style and this will lead towards the assimilation of other culture in chitral. To preserve the culture of chitral it is essential to create a balance between globalization and culture of Chitral. To preserve the tradition of chitral, the introduction of chitral local language i.e. (Khowar) must be integrated with Urdu and English language in schools, colleges. Additionly, in schools the traditional seminars should also be held in which the students must be known about their culture heritage by their elders. Creating awareness among chitral people to take pride in their traditional culture will be a good source to preserve the traditional culture of Chitral.

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